

BRAND Guidelines

TERRAVISION

The purpose of this guide is to assist the Consortium in using the TERRAVISION logo correctly and maintaining the integrity of the project's overall brand identity. It is also a useful aid when instructing typographers and others employed to produce branded items to design and create TERRAVISION communications material

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Brand Logo

The idea behind

SIGN DESIGN //

Lines in parallel formations //

They refer to the soil layers as they are formed in a mine area. These lines are nested within a closed circle shape, they define the area and give the concept of land. The smaller outer circle has the meaning of the satellite.

COLORS //

Gamma of green

The colors suggested are inspired by coloring rocks. The green color also has the meaning of the “green economy” included in the philosophy project.

TYPOGRAPHY //

Clean and simple font in the name TERRAVISION, with an extra volume in height. The separation of the word/noun, and the differentiation into italics and normal gives the emphasis that a clear visual effect needs.

Logo Variations

Positive Format (Primary Format)

Primarily the logo should be used on a white background in its positive format for maximum impact and clarity. In cases where this is not feasible, the versions on page 6 are available for usage.

Logo Variations

a) Negative Format:

This format of the TERRAVISION logo is only used when placing the logo on an image, a colored background or a pattern.

b) BW/Grayscale Formats

These logo variations are meant to be printed in a grayscale or black and white format (i.e. internal memos).

Color Pallet

Main Colors

CMYK = **C75 M68 Y68 K90**
RGB = **R9 G82 B74**
#3b524a

CMYK = **C34 M0 Y31 K0**
RGB = **R171 G214 B189**
#abd6bd

Additional Colors

CMYK = **C0 M7 Y16 K0**
RGB = **R217 G223 B212**
#F4BB39

CMYK = **C28 M35 Y47 K0**
RGB = **R188 G162 B137**
#bca289

CMYK = **C13 M70 Y70 K0**
RGB = **R212 G108 B82**
#e28484

MAIN and ADDITIONAL COLORS

CMYK colors are used in printing material.
RGB colors are used on web applications

Additional color palletete can be used for layouts and artworks such as website/posters/leaflets e.t.c. in case you need a small touch of color contrast. These colors cannot replace main color palletete or logotype official colors

Logo Usage

The Clear Space zone around the logo has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of the TERRAVISION logotype. Maintaining the Clear Space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc. ensures that the TERRAVISION logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separate from any other visuals. To make sure the logo is always clear and legible, a minimum size requirement was determined. However, when using a lower quality printing technique (i.e. screenprinting), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

LOGOTYPE PRINT minimum size
31 mm W X 15 mm H

LOGOTYPE SCREEN minimum size
112 px W | 58 px H

Logo Improper use

Display the TERRAVISION logo only in the formats that are specified in this guide.

The TERRAVISION logo may not appear in any other colors than the already specified in page 7 of this guide.

Do not rotate, skew, scale, redraw, alter or distort the TERRAVISION logo in any way.

Do not combine the TERRAVISION logo with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

Logo usage on social media

Logo use on social media: the logo should be used in a white background.

Logo usage on backgrounds

When placing the logo on an image, color or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background. The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

Typography brand

Must be always used to all communications material and in web and media applications wherever this is possible (i.e. at the TERRAVISION website), to retain consistency. Replacing the given typeface with others should not be done under any circumstances.

Roboto fonts family

Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Light

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Thin

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Medium

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz**

Bold

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz**

Black

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz**

You can download the font family here

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Roboto?preview.text=Whenever%20I%20go&subset=greek¬o.script=Grek>

Typography brand

1) For MS templates and publications

HEADING 1

Calibri bold,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2

Calibri bold,
16pt, blue colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3

Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 4

Calibri bold,
14pt, blue colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

Body text

Calibri-Regular, 11pt, black colors

2) For Website and other web-applications

HEADING 1

Roboto, black,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2

Roboto, Bold,
16pt, black colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3

Roboto, Bold,
14pt, black colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 4

Roboto, Medium,
14pt, black colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

Body text

Roboto, Regular, 11pt, black colors

3) For leaflets and other material

HEADING 1

Roboto, black,
18pt black colors

HEADING 2

Roboto, Bold,
16pt, black colors
(RGB R37 G60 B126)

HEADING 3

Roboto, Bold,
14pt, black colors (RGB R37 G60
B126)

HEADING 4

Roboto, Medium,
14pt, black colors (RGB R37 G60 B126)

Body text

Roboto, Regular, 11pt, black colors

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